

INFLUENCES TO THE STUDENTS' CHOICE OF A TRACK AND A STRAND AMONG GRADE 10 STUDENTS OF CRISTO REY HIGH SCHOOL: AN ANALYSIS

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Influences to the Students' Choice of a Track and a Strand Among Grade 10 Students of Cristo Rey High School: An Analysis

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Abstract

The study aimed to describe and analyze the influences to the students' choice of a track and strand in senior high school among grade 10 students of Cristo Rey High School. Employing the descriptive-correlational method of research, 253 respondents were chosen using random sampling technique from different year levels were surveyed using the questionnaire method. Frequency and mean computation were utilized in describing the influences under childhood aspirations, family/relative influences, peer/friends influences, values, perceive in-demand jobs, socio-economic status, and school guidance counselor. Whereas, Pearson-Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was the statistical treatment used to relate the influences with the respondents' age, gender, scholastic aptitude, family monthly income, and parental educational attainment. The research study revealed that among the identified influences, the most influenced was values. Moreover, in-demand jobs were also found to have a significant relationship with the influences of the respondents in choosing a track and strand in senior high school. At the end of the study, an analysis was proposed and the implication of this study to educational management was set out. Since the findings surfaced matters about the influences that students faced with, the study recommended that family and school should work hand in hand to shaped the future of our students by motivating them in choosing the right track and strand for their senior high school.

Keywords: *students, strand, analysis, track, senior high school*

Introduction

Basic education is the inalienable right of every Filipino citizen. This is since universal education is an inescapable corollary of universal suffrage. The better the education the citizens received, the better person they become. For, as Plato said: "The best man makes the citizens."

Change is inevitable and immutable law of nature. With the Philippine education continuing to overwhelm and the student performance remain less than of what it should be, internal or external stakeholders alike have been calling for the kind of reform that would finally see the country's educational system out of crisis – or what Education Secretary Brother Armin Luistro characterizes as chronic illness (Teves et al., 2011). The reform – minded President Aquino, had campaigned on a proposal to lessen poverty and enhance the competitiveness of the Philippines by investing in quality education.

The Department of Education and allied stakeholders are responding to the urgent and critical need to improve the quality of basic education in the Philippines through a major reform known as K to 12, which means kindergarten and the six years of elementary and six years of secondary education. A well-crafted curriculum design becomes valuable only when it is properly implemented. Undeniably, the implementation of the curriculum is a major educational concern. It is a management function that needs careful attention on the effective delivery of the curriculum design. In recent times, school education has emerged as an important segment of the total educational system expected to contribute significantly to the individual as well as the national development process. The first batch of the Filipino students to go through Grade 11 will troop to schools in 2016. Many students and parents, though, are still unaware of a few details as regards the new senior high school system. Matters on the country's K-12 program remain unclear. One of them however, refers to the specific tracks wherein students will choose the best skill for them to master. With the new educational system required by the government, Filipinos have no other choice but to embrace it. In the first place, each one will profit from the new scheme because it follows international standard.

The Department of Education (DepEd) urged its regional offices to look at the economy in their areas to determine which senior high school (SHS) tracks they should focus on. According to the Manual of the Implementation of Senior High School in Region III, the K to 12 basic education curriculum prepares students with lifelong skills that they can earn while schooling.

The curriculum will enable the students to acquire Certificates of Competency (COCs) and National Certificates (NCs) issued by the Technical Skills Development Authority (TESDA). These NCs specify that K to 12 graduates have acquired middle level skills and will have better opportunities for gainful employment. The additional years will also ensure that K to 12 graduates are better prepared for college. Starting school year 2016-2017, there will be "Grade 11". It signals the beginning of the Senior High School which is a major reform in the Philippine Secondary Education. Senior High School added two years of specialized upper secondary education. The choice of track will define the content of the subjects a student will take in Grade 11 and Grade 12. These subjects fall under the core curriculum or career pathways. Of course, that reform is part of the bigger K to 12 project of President Aquino.

Apart from the core curriculum, which has eight learning areas, the new senior high school system comes with specific career tracks that seem like college courses. They include certain disciplines. Academic, Arts and Design, Sports, and Technical-Vocational-

Livelihood (TVL) are the tracks in Senior High School. Academic track prepares students who plan to pursue college education and comprises four strands:

- a. Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM);
- b. Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM);
- c. Humanities and Social Science; and d. General Academic.

The next three tracks equip students with the skills needed to secure jobs in the field they want: Arts and Design, this track covers nine subjects, eight of which require 80 hours each per semester; Sports, this track has nine subjects, which include Safety and First Aid, Human Movement, Coaching, Sports Officiating, and Sports Leadership; Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL), this track contains nine subjects (known as the TVL track subjects) and TESDA specialized subjects such as Home Economics, Agri-Fishery, Industrial Arts and Information and Communications Technology or ICT. Each senior high school student must choose one track to master and base his/her choice on how he/she wants to advance after completing high school on Grade 12. Career assessment and aptitude tests and an occupational interest inventory, in the contrary, will show the student's strengths and interests. Career advocacy programs will also help and guide them in choosing the right track for their selves. With the end view of the full implementation of Senior High School in school year 2016-2017, the DepEd shall ensure that all Grade 10 completers, including those outside the formal education system, are enrolled in the senior high school. Furthermore, the DepEd, through the senior high school career guidance program shall assist senior high school entrants in making informed decisions regarding their choice and track and promote awareness in the importance of choosing a track that suits their skills and interests that matches the available resources and needs of the society (DepEd Order no.41, s. 2015). There are these influences that affect a student in choosing a track and a strand in senior high school and plan well for their future. Influences such as socio-economic status, family/relatives, peers/friends, in-demand jobs and guidance counselors/career advocates affect the decision making of a student and that different suggestions and notions gurgles in his/her mind. It is for this reason that this study of the "Influences to the Students in Choice of a Track and Strand Among Grade 10 Students in Cristo Rey High School: An Analysis" will be conducted to address concerns of these influences for secondary schools in the Division of Tarlac Province.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the influences on the students' choice of a track and a strand among grade 10 students of Cristo Rey High School. Specifically, this study answered to the following questions:

1. What are the top expressed tracks choices of the students as to:
 - 1.1 Academic Track
 - 1.1.1 general academic strand (GAS);
 - 1.1.2 humanities and social sciences strand (HUMSS);
 - 1.1.3 science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM); and
 - 1.1.4 accountancy, business and management (ABM)?
 - 1.2 Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Track
 - 1.2.1 home economic strand; and
 - 1.2.1.1 beauty care?
 - 1.2.2 information and communications technology (ICT)
 - 1.2.2.1 animations
2. How are the grade 10 students of Cristo Rey High School described in terms of the influences:
 - 2.1 childhood aspirations;
 - 2.2 family/relatives influence;
 - 2.3 peer/friends influence;
 - 2.4 values;
 - 2.5 perceive in-demand jobs;
 - 2.6 socio-economic status; and
 - 2.7 school guidance counselor influence?
3. What influence related to the expressed tracks and strands of the study?
4. What are the anticipated problems encountered in making their tracks and strands choice?
5. What analysis can be drawn based on the findings of the study?
6. What implications can be drawn from the results of the study to educational management?

Methodology

This section presents and describes the methodologies used in the study. The research design, research locale, the respondents, the research instrument and data gathering procedures and the statistical treatments used are all described in this chapter.

Research Design

In this study, descriptive design will be used. It will describe the influences student’s choice of a track and a strand in senior high school of the K to 12 curriculum among grade10 students of Cristo Rey High School. The research intended to present and describe on how the students faced these influences on their decision in choosing a track and a strand and determine the possible problems encountered by the Grade 10 students of Cristo Rey High School. The survey method will be used as the major technique in generating data.

Descriptive research will be used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena to describe “what exists” with respect to variables or conditions in a situation (Brg & Gall, 1992). The main goal of this type of research is to describe the data and characteristics about what will be studied and to study frequencies, averages, and other statistical calculations.

Participants

The Grade 10 students of Cristo Rey High School will be the main respondents of the study.

Instruments

The researcher will utilize the questionnaire in gathering data. Documentary analysis will also use to supplement the data through the questionnaires. Relevant documents will be searched, requested and analyzed.

They survey questionnaire is the main tool in gathering data. The researcher will design and construct questions based on related studies, books, manuals and other sources suited to the nature of the study. DepEd Order 31 s. 2012 which was “Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) Effective School Year “2012-2013” and the Senior High School Implementation Plan Region III-Central Luzon will be used to formulate the questions.

Set of questionnaires will be given to the Grade 10 students of Cristo Rey High School to gather the needed data and information and as well as to identify the influences on their decisions in choosing their track and strand as they face the initial implementation of the senior high school of the K to 12 curriculum.

The last part of the questionnaire will consist of the possible problems that will be encountered by the respondents in the implementation of senior high school and the influences on their choices and decisions. Previous studies with similar concern will also consulted to modify and clarify the question that will be presented.

Procedure

The researcher will sought permission to look into some official records and documents of the concerned schools from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Tarlac Province and the School Principals of Cristo Rey High School. Questionnaires will be intended for the grade 10 students of the said school and will be personally hand carried. The said school will be visited personally for the scrutiny of records and documents.

Results and Discussion

1. What are the top expressed tracks and strands choices of the students?

<i>Track and Strand in Senior High School</i>	<i>Course Name of the Track and Strand in Senior High School</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
2	Humanities and Social Sciences Strand (HUMSS)	76
3	Science and Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM)	53
4	Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)	46
17	Computer Programing	27
14	Tourism	12
10	Cookery	9
1	General Academic Strand (GAS)	7
12	Food and Beverages	6
16	Animations	6
19	Agricultural Crop Production	2
40	Automotive Servicing	2
49	Sports Track	2
7	Beauty Care	1
8	Bread and Pastry	1
11	Dress Making	1
20	Animal Healthcare Management	1
46	Shielded Metal Arc Welding	1
Others	Other Tracks and Strand not listed above	0

The most expressed tracks and strands among the grade 10 students falls under the academic track which is Humanities and Social Sciences also known as HUMSS. 76 among 253 respondents choose this strand to be their occupational interest when they will reach their senior high school. Next in rank is also under the same track, this strand is Science and Technology, Engineering and Mathematics also known as STEM. 53 respondents choose this strand to be their first interest in entering senior high school. This is also followed in ranked under academic track which is Accountancy, Business and Management or ABM, wherein 46 students marked this as their interest strand for their incoming senior high school.

Computer Programming got the fourth spot with 27 respondents in this strand. Even though this strand is not offered at present in Cristo Rey High School, the students are still looking forward to choose their primary interest course for their senior high school level. After computer Programming, Tourism follows with 12 students that chooses this strand. Next in rank is Cookery with 9 students, followed by General Academic Strand also known as GAS with 7 students that chooses this to be their interest then Food and Beverages and Animations with both 6 students that marked this strand. There are three strands that both 2 students checked these to be their occupational interest and these are Agricultural Crop Production, Automotive Servicing and Sports Track. Being on the last in rank, Beauty Care, Bread and Pastry, Dress Making, Animal Healthcare Management and Shielded Metal Arc Welding, they all got the same 1 student that marked them as their interest in entering senior high school.

2. Influences of Career Path Among grade 10 Students of Cristo Rey High School

1.1 Childhood Aspirations

<i>Childhood Aspirations</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. I dream of becoming what I want to pursue a career.	3.92	Moderately Influential
2. I saw myself as a career driven person.	3.20	Influential
3. I am particularly interested in this career that I'll pursue from this track.	4.06	Moderately Influential
4. I see myself as competent at this career that I'll pursue from this track.	3.82	Moderately Influential
5. This is what I dream when I was a child.	3.26	Influential
6. I always look myself to be someone successful.	4.42	Moderately Influential
7. I want to become what I want when I was a child.	3.55	Influenced Moderately
8. This match the career that I want.	3.71	Moderately Influential
9. The available strand in this school is what I want to become	3.43	Influential
10. The available track in this school is what I want to become	3.42	Influential
Grand Mean	3.68	Moderately Influential

In this influence, number six marks the highest points. This reflects that every student really dream to become successful. Second in rank is number three. This shows that what they want to pursue is what they want to be someday. Next in rank is number one. This shows that every students had their dreams and to reach those dreams that they have. Ranked 8, being on the least part, shows that there are strand that students want to pursue but are not offered in their present school. Ranked 9 reflect that students are not focusing right now on their dreams when they were a child but they even change in decisions. The last rank this shows the impact of modernization that affect the students in becoming a career driven person.

1.2 Family/Relatives influence

<i>Family/Relatives influence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. My parents and/or relatives took the same career that I would pursue.	3.07	Influential
2. Preferences are made by a relative since they will provide for the expenses.	2.96	Influential
3. My family will give me support on the chosen career for me.	4.22	Moderately Influential
4. I believe that they are the one who are responsible to choose a career for me since they may know what is best for me.	3.21	Influential
5. Having a degree holder parents influence my choosing a track and strand.	3.00	Influential
6. Seek advice to my parents to what track and strand I would pursue	3.40	Influential
7. Seek advice to my relatives to what track and strand I would pursue	2.94	Influential
8. My parents told me to pursue this kind of career.	3.29	Influential
9. My relatives told me to pursue this kind of career.	2.94	Influential
10. The profession in my family is also my preferred course.	2.42	Slightly Influential
Grand Mean	3.15	Influential

With regards to family/relatives influence, number 3 mark the highest point. This shows that the family is the number one supporter of the students in their studies. Second in rank is number 6. It reflects that the students still ask advice to their parents before deciding on what to pursue. Third in rank is number eight. There are still parents that mandate their children on what to pursue a career in their life. The top 3 least influential shows that there are students that even seek advice to their relatives but still their parents give most influential than they are. With this, there are students wherein their relatives are the one who supports their studies. Number 10, being on the least part, it gives us information that the profession of the family still affects the decision of the students but it also shows that the students are already matured to decide what to pursue.

1.3 Peer/ Friends influence

<i>Peer/ Friends influence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. This is the track and strand that my friends will pursue	2.27	Slightly Influential
2. I would like to follow my peers/friends.	1.94	Slightly Influential
3. I follow the advice of my peers/friends.	2.31	Slightly Influential
4. Peers/friends advices can be good and relevant to my situation.	2.77	Influential
5. Friends in this new generation can be a tool in taking the right thing included the course that I will take.	2.63	Influential
6. My friends/peers decided that we will pursue this kind of track and strand.	2.32	Slightly Influential
7. My peers/friends are the one who will decide what career we will pursue.	2.02	Slightly Influential
8. Peers/friends assist me in deciding what to pursue in my career	2.54	Influential
9. Peers/friends offer advice just because they think they can help you.	2.86	Influential
10. I do believe in what my friends/peers said.	2.38	Slightly Influential
Grand Mean	2.40	Slightly Influential

Under this influence, it is already on the sequence that peers/friends are not that influential in terms of career decision making. The most influential in this aspect is number 9. The peers/friends still has a role of giving advice having in mind that they would be a help to them. They still believe that they will give a good advice to them. The second in rank is under number four. This is in line with the first in rank, wherein the peers and friends think that they can give a good advice to help their friends have a good decision/s in pursuing a career. Number five marked the third rank. This reflects that peers/friends in this new generation serve as a tool in choosing a career. The new generation in this era, thinks they can be a good help and tool for their friends.

The least three show that peers/friends don't give that huge impact in the decision making of the students. In this era, students can decide on their own and build their career even if it cause isolation from their peers/friends.

1.4 Values

<i>Values</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. I look the goodness of the course I will take.	4.43	Moderately Influential
2. This will follow the values that I believe.	4.09	Moderately Influential
3. It will enhance the goodness in me.	4.05	Moderately Influential
4. My values affect my decisions to what track and strand to take.	3.45	Influential
5. The track and strand I will choose will not change my belief.	3.64	Moderately Influential
6. The track and strand will boost the values that I practice in my life.	3.68	Moderately Influential
7. I consider the values on the track and strand I will take.	3.75	Moderately Influential
8. I let the track and strand will change the values that I believe and practice.	3.15	Influential
9. The track and strand I will choose will develop my values.	3.83	Moderately Influential
10. The track and strand I will choose will make me a better person.	3.42	Influential
Grand Mean	3.75	Moderately Influential

The influence under values marked the highest influence. This shows that students still look and considered the goodness/values in every action and in the course that they will take. The first ranked in values influence is number one. This shows that students still look the values in actions and in under the track and strand they will pursue. Next in rank reflects that the track and strand they will choose contains the values that they believe. This doesn't contradict one's own values and even to destroy it. The third ranked under values influence which is number three shows that students choose the track and strand that enhance the values that they believe. It emblemize the improvement of goodness that they have and to develop it more.

The 3rd least influence shows that the values that they have and follow has an effect in their decision making on choosing a career. But it is still on how to improve their values and not to deteriorate it matters most to them. The nine placer at the bottom shows that students think on how to become a better person, but in this era, they think better on how to develop their skills by not deteriorating their values in life. On the last ranked item, the students allow the track and strand that they will choose to change the values that they have. This shows that the students would think first of the goodness or values on what to choose rather than letting it to affect the values that they have.

1.5 Perceive In-Demand Jobs

<i>Perceive In-Demand Jobs</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. There are abundant opportunities I can avail from the career I would pursue.	3.62	Moderately Influential
2. The track that I chose will help me to find a suitable career easily.	3.72	Moderately Influential
3. The career that I would pursue is timely in-demand.	3.48	Influential
4. I am fully aware of the opportunities that surround the career I seek.	3.58	Moderately Influential
5. I will gain additional knowledge to be equipped in the timely job that I want.	3.77	Moderately Influential
6. This is the most popular job now a day.	3.32	Influential
7. I consider my course choice to be an in-demand course.	3.34	Influential

8. The availability of job in the future affects my choice of track and strand.	3.44	Influential
9. I look the in-demand jobs in the future and not just the present.	3.70	Moderately Influential
10. The in-demand jobs affect my decisions in choosing the track and strand I will take.	3.44	Influential
Grand Mean	3.54	Moderately Influential

Under this influence, the top most influential item is number 5. This means that the students are already looking forward on gaining knowledge and skills to be suitable and apt in the timely job that they are looking forward to have. The second top most influential item under In-demand job shows that they are choosing the track and strand that will help them find a job and career more easily than others. This is by seeing that the track and strand they will choose gives a lot of opportunities for them in the future and for their future as well. The third in rank indicates that the students think of the future in demand jobs and not just the present. They already know that the in-demand jobs for now maybe different in the future, that is why it is good to see that they are already looking in the future.

Numbers eight and ten ranked as the third in the last influential among items. It reflects that in-demands job affects the decision making of the students on what to choose. Also, the future really matters on choosing a career. It is good to see that the orientation for the students regarding on choosing a career imbued among the students. Not knowing what to be in the future in-demand jobs, the students pay attention to every orientation to choose the best for their future. Next in ranked serves an output research that students look their choice track and strand as an in-demand course. This is to see that the students are looking on the in-demand jobs in the future and not just the in-demand course now-a-days. In line with this, the last in rank among items under this influence shows that the students are not focused on the present situation of the in-demand jobs rather than they are already matured to think what to be in the future when they are on the point of entering a job or taking a course in the college.

1.6 Socio-economic Status

<i>Socio-economic Status</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. This is the course suited in our family status.	3.15	Influential
2. Our family cannot afford the expenses in pursuing my career in other school.	2.89	Influential
3. This is the track and strand available in the school near us.	3.25	Influential
4. I consider the financial status of my family in choosing my track and strand I will take.	3.40	Influential
5. My father is the only bread winner in the family.	2.72	Influential
6. My parents do not have a permanent job.	2.49	Slightly Influential
7. Our family status cannot afford the track and strand I want to pursue	2.54	Influential
8. My parents' salary will not suffice our needs in the family if I will pursue my studies in other school	2.69	Influential
9. I consider our numbers in our family and our status in choosing track and strand.	2.85	Influential
10. Money is also an issue in choosing a career.	3.42	Influential
Grand Mean	2.94	Influential

The influence under socio-economic status, the top most ranked which is number ten, shows that money is an issue in choosing a track and strand in senior high school. It reflects that the students also think of the sources of the possible expenses in their studies. This is also in line with the second in rank most influential item under this influence, wherein it says that the students also consider their financial status. This shows the fact that each students think of money as a best help in their studies. The third in rank shows that students considered the available tracks and strands in the school near them or on the school they are currently enrolled. This is to save money for transportation and to use it on a more useful way. The least three among the item influences indicates the effects of inadequacy of funds on the decision making of the students in choosing what to take in senior high school. But even if this insufficiency affects it, the volition of the students to pursue and look forward for the betterment of their future matters most to them. This indicates that the will is better than hindrances.

1.7 School Guidance Counselor influence

<i>School Guidance Counselor influence</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. Quality of career guidance program.	3.53	Moderately Influential
2. Assisted in the career path that I will choose.	3.33	Influential
3. Motivated my will to pursue the track and strand that I want to choose.	3.63	Moderately Influential
4. Advice of guidance counselor.	3.04	Influential
5. Guidance counselor is the greatest influence in choosing my career.	2.81	Influential
6. I believe in the school guidance counselor	3.34	Influential
7. I consult our school guidance counselor in choosing the track and strand I will take	2.56	Influential
8. You acquire information from the school guidance counselor before making choices.	2.79	Influential
9. Guidance counselor's advice can be good and relevant in your situation.	2.97	Influential
10. I listen to our school guidance counselor.	3.02	Influential
Grand Mean	3.10	Influential

The most influential item under the school guidance counselor influence falls in number 3 which means the students sees the importance of the guidance counselor in motivating their will to pursue in their studies. Second in rank is number one, wherein it shows that the

students believe in the quality of the career guidance program. Their participation lift-up their will to pursue the career of their likes. The third in ranked mark in number 6. The students believe in the school guidance counselor that they can be a good help and motivator to evaluate their skills and to pursue on achieving their goal.

Ranked 8 in item influence is number 5. The students also see the guidance counselor as someone that influences their decisions in choosing what career to take, but the school guidance counselor guides the students in choosing the career and not to be one deciding on what course the students will take. Next in the least rank is number 8. This shows that even if some of the students seek information on the school guidance counselor, it is still their decision that matters. The information gives additional knowledge to the students but their will what to pursue will be on their personal decision. The last in rank is number 9. This reflects that even the students consults the school guidance counselor, still the final say on that to choose lies on the decision of each students.

3. What influence related to the expressed tracks and strands of the study?

Profile	Test Statistics	Influences						
		CA	FRI	PFI	Val	PIJ	SES	SSGI
Age Group	Pearson Correlation	.073	-.013	-.151 *	.143*	.107	-.051	-.014
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.244	.832	.016	.023	.089	.420	.823
	N	253	253	253	253	253	253	253
Sex	Pearson Correlation	.078	.041	-.108	.037	.002	.017	.023
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.214	.521	.087	.562	.978	.788	.714
	N	253	253	253	253	253	253	253
Scholastic Aptitude	Pearson Correlation	-.070	.104	.148*	-.069	-.207**	.195**	-.068
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.270	.098	.019	.271	.001	.002	.283
	N	253	253	253	253	253	253	253
Family Income	Pearson Correlation	.054	.027	-.081	.077	-.193**	.221**	-.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.389	.668	.199	.224	.002	.000	.601
	N	253	253	253	253	253	253	253
Parents Educational Attainment	Pearson Correlation	.198**	.045	-.087	.076	.082	-.153*	.018
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.479	.169	.226	.193	.015	.777
	N	253	253	253	253	253	253	253

Under age group, we can see on the data that gathering a -.151, it shows that those who are younger can be easily influence by peers/friends and those who are older cannot be easily influence by their peers/friends. Gathering .143 under values, those who are older, think much of their values unlike the younger ones. Under sex, with any gender, all of them can be influenced under these influences.

In scholastic aptitude, under peer/friends influences, those who have a high grade can be influence by their friends with the same level. They are looking on a course that for them would be good on their grades. Having a .195, those who get a high grades are being influence to get a high salary in the future. Since they know that they have a high grades they are looking forward that someday they will have a high salary in their jobs. But for those who have lower grades, they are already thinking on a job, that is why they are looking for a vocational course. They are after the job and not focusing on a high salary.

Under family income, the influences gathering -.193 shows that the students who have an insufficient funds in their family are being influence more in in-demand jobs. They want to find a job so that they can help in the family when it comes into financial matters. Having .221 under socio-economic status, means that for those who have much they are being influence to get a course that they would think getting a high salary and focused on their studies.

In parental educational attainment, .198 in childhood aspirations show that they are being influence on the educational attainment of their parents. They see their parents doing things that influence them in thinking that by someday they would do the same. They dream on becoming their parents. With -.153 in socio-economic status indicates that those parents who were not graduated in college would like to see their children graduated. The students were being influenced because of their current situation in family and ended up motivating themselves to finish their studies and pursuing their career so that they could be a great help someday.

4. What are the anticipated problems encountered in making their tracks and strands choice?

Anticipated Problems	Number of Respondents
1. Financial Status	175
2. Health Condition	14
3. Family Relationship	19
4. The track and strand I want is not available in the school I am presently studying.	31
5. Bullying	9
6. Others	5

Specify:

Dito na sila lumipat.

Kukunin na kasi siya ng Tita niya sa
Manila para mag-aral.

Dito kasi nagtuturo ang tatay niya.

Gusto niya subukan ang ibang paaralan.

Problems may hinder one's dreams and goals in achieving it. It is inevitable and part of our existence on earth. It may be seen as to deteriorate your volition and strength or to mold you to be stronger and become a better person. The top ranked in the most anticipated problem is number 1, financial status. It shows that money really matters in pursuing a career or studies especially when the fund in a family is inadequate for them. As we can see in the table 1.6 which is Socio-Economic Status, it shows that the highest influential item says that money is also an issue in choosing a career. But it is good to see that the students are still motivated in pursuing a career that in one day may change their life.

Our health condition has also an impact in choosing the track and strand in senior high school. There are instances that because of a poor health, it causes the students to stop in pursuing their career or to change the course that they want.

There is a great influence to the students when we talk about family. We cannot remove the fact that the family supports each member in any career that they will take. As we can see in table 1.2, number 3 where it says that "My family will give me support on the chosen career for me," shows that family will support each other. For this reason, their relationships will affect the students will on continuing their studies. The unity among family members matters in pursuing the career of the students.

The availability of the track and strand in the school has a big impact in the decision making of the students. There is a possibility that some of the students will just change their first choice of interest and choose among the tracks and strands that the school offers where they are currently enrolled.

Victims of bullying leave psychological effects in each students. This also may effect in the decision making of the students on what to choose for their senior high school. Other anticipated problems that were specified show that due to their migration on this barangay, they will enroll on the school near them and enroll on what the school offers. There are also students that will enroll in other school because of the support coming from their niece and to enroll on their interest track and strand in senior high school. The other student will just enroll on the school where is father is teaching to save from other expenses.

5. What analysis can be drawn based on the findings of the study?

Showing all the data gathered in this research, the most expressed track and strand falls under academic track. It reflects that students are looking forward in the future in-demand jobs and not just the present. Under academic tracks, there are a lot of courses offered in college that are in line in the studies and subjects in this track. Most of these students are planning to pursue their studies in college. The other remaining expressed tracks and strands are under technical-vocational courses that enhance and develop the skills of the students. This is to prepare them if they want to go on work or to build their own business after senior high school. They can also go to college if they want to pursue their studies.

Showing all the different influences given in this research, the students marked the items differently that depends how these affect them. Values serves as the most influential among these different influences which means that the students are considering the values and goodness that have or practiced in life. They are still looking on the goodness of the track and strand that they will take for their senior high school.

Based from the tabulated data, peer/friends influences ranked to be the lowest which shows that the students are already matured enough to decide on what to take in senior high school. They will decide on what to take based form what they see and what they feel and will not rely on the decisions of their peers/friends. They will not be affected that much in the influences of the peers/friends in their decision making on what track and strand to choose.

The relations between these influences show a negative and positive output that reflects the balance of the gathered data. Looking on the anticipated problems of the students in entering senior high school, the top most ranked among these is financial status. It shows that money has a great impact in pursuing the career or studies of the students. For some students, they do not pursue their studies because of this problem. It is good to see that students even having a problem about financial stability, they are still motivated to pursue their studies and continue their career.

6. What implications can be drawn from the results of the study to educational management?

The result of the study shows that influences on the students' choice of a track and strand in senior high school plays a role in the decision making of the students. It reflects that these influences may lead the students on what career the will pursue in

senior high. With this research, the school can continue to improve its program that will help in motivating the students and guiding them in career that they would like to pursue. These influences give light to enrich the volition of the students in pursuing the career they would like to enroll.

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